

Studies on Imidazolines and Benzimidazoles. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-(2'-Aryl-6'/7'-substituted-quinolin-4'-yl)-4,5-dihydroimidazoles/benzimidazoles and their Mannich Bases

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2-Aryl-6/7-substituted-4-quinolinecarboxylic acids have been condensed with ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamines to give imidazolines and benzimidazoles, respectively. The products are condensed with formaldehyde, diethylamine and *N,N*-diethylaminoethanol. These have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

IN view of the reported wide therapeutic activity of imidazolines¹ and benzimidazoles², the synthesis of imidazolines and benzimidazoles derivatives of type 1 and 2 was undertaken to study their biological properties. 2-Aryl-6/7-substituted-4-quinolinecarboxylic acids³ were condensed with ethylenediamine and *o*-phenylenediamine in the presence of polyphosphoric acid at 160°* to yield imidazolines (1) and benzimidazoles (2), respectively. The products were then condensed with formaldehyde and diethyl amine using ethanol as solvent. The ir spectra of imidazoline reveal bands at 3 350 (NH), 1 260 (C-N) and 1;240 cm⁻¹ (Ar-O-R),

hydroxyphenyl-6-methyl/6-chloro, *A. niger* (22); 2-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-7-nitro, *M. cressa* (19); 2-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-6'-methyl, *Penicillium* (20); in case of benzimidazole.

2'-*p*-Hydroxyphenyl-7'-nitro (22) and 6'-methyl (20), *E. coli*; 7'-methyl and 6'-chloro, *S. typhosa* (20); incase of its Mannich bases, 7'-methyl, *S. aureus* (20), *E. coli* (18); 2'-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-6'-chloro, *N. cressa* (18), *A. niger* (20); 2-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-7-methyl, *N. cressa* (20); *A. niger* (18), *Penicillium* (20). Mannich bases from benzimidazol, 2-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-7'-methyl, *N. cressa* (20), *A. niger* (18), *Penicillium* (20); 2-*p*-hydroxy-6'-methoxy, *N. cressa* (20), *A. niger* (14), *Penicillium* (20).

R₁, R₂, R₃ = Me, OMe, Cl, NO₂, X = H, OH, N(C₂H₅)₂,

while benzimidazole at 3 300 (NH), 1 255 (Ar-O-R) and 1 310 cm⁻¹ (C-N).

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were tested for antimicrobial activity by cup-plate method⁵ using dioxan as solvent at a concentration of 50 μg ml⁻¹, and compared with the known antibiotic chloromycetin. Maximum activity was recorded in case of imidazoline derivatives. The compound, microorganism and zone of inhibition (mm) are as follows: 2'-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-6'-methyl and 2'-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-7'-chloro, *S. aureus* (26), *E. coli* (18) and *S. typhosa* (36); and 2-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-7'-chloro, *N. cressa* (26), *A. niger* (22) and *Penicillium* (20); in case of Mannich bases, 2-*p*-

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Spectromom 2000 spectrophotometer. 2-Aryl-6/7-substituted-4-quinolinecarboxylic acids were prepared as reported³ (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-ARYL-6/7-SUBSTITUTED-QUINOLINE-4-CARBOXYLIC ACIDS*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	Mol. formula	Yield %	M.p. °C
1.	OH	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NO ₃	56	227-30
2.	OH	OCH ₃	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NO ₃	58	168-70
3.	OH	H	CH ₃	—	—	236
4.	OH	CH ₃	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NO ₃	52	205
5.	OH	H	NO ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	48	119-20
6.	OH	NO ₂	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	50	170d
7.	OH	H	Cl	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ ClNO ₃	58	240d
8.	OH	Cl	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ ClNO ₃	59	139-41
9.	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₃	50	178-80
10.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	—	—	212
11.	OCH ₃	H	CH ₃	—	—	186
12.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₃	55	195
13.	OCH ₃	H	NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	51	120-55
14.	OCH ₃	NO ₂	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₅	52	182-85
15.	OCH ₃	H	Cl	—	—	220
16.	OCH ₃	Cl	H	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ClNO ₃	58	184-85

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(2'-ARYL-6'/7'-SUBSTITUTED-QUINOLIN-4'-YL)-4,5-DIHYDROIMIDAZOLES*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X	Mol formula	Yield %	M.p. °C
1.	OH	H	OOH ₂	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	56	247
2.	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	57	225
3.	OH	H	CH ₃	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	57	215
4.	OH	CH ₃	H	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	58	190
5.	OH	H	NO ₂	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃	55	205
6.	OH	NO ₂	H	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃	56	268
7.	OH	H	Cl	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂	55	244
8.	OH	Cl	H	H	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O	54	244
9.	OCH ₃	H	OOH ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	52	146
10.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	55	195
11.	OCH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	50	202
12.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	52	236d
13.	OCH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃	56	173
14.	OCH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃	54	244
15.	OCH ₃	H	Cl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O	54	202d
16.	OCH ₃	Cl	H	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O	55	236d
17.	OH	H	OOH ₂	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	48	325
18.	OH	OCH ₃	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	47	285
19.	OH	H	CH ₃	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	48	325
20.	OH	CH ₃	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	48	230d
21.	OH	H	NO ₂	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃	49	280d
22.	OH	NO ₂	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃	47	296d
23.	OH	H	Cl	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	46	136d
24.	OH	Cl	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	45	214
25.	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	50	236d
26.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	51	278d
27.	OCH ₃	H	CH ₃	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	48	325
28.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	47	276d
29.	OCH ₃	H	NO ₂	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	46	235d
30.	OCH ₃	NO ₂	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	47	211
31.	OCH ₃	H	Cl	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₃ O	45	286d
32.	OCH ₃	Cl	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ ClN ₃ O	44	

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

TABLE 3—PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-(2'-ARYL-6'/7'-SUBSTITUTED-QUINOLIN-4'-YL)-BENZAMIDAZOLES*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	X	Mol formula	Yield %	M.p. °C
1.	OH	H	OCH	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	57	294d
2.	OH	OCH ₃	H	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	58	250
3.	OH	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	54	267
4.	OH	CH ₃	H	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂	53	282
5.	OH	H	NO ₂	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃	53	239
6.	OH	NO ₂	H	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃	54	217
7.	OH	H	Cl	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O	55	222
8.	OH	Cl	H	H	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₃ O	55	214
9.	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	59	189
10.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	58	188
11.	OCH ₃	H	CH ₃	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	59	223
12.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	56	212
13.	OCH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃	58	249
14.	OCH ₃	NO ₂	H	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₃	57	238
15.	OCH ₃	H	Cl	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O	53	118
16.	OCH ₃	Cl	H	H	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O	54	162
17.	OH	H	OCH ₃	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	45	268d
18.	OH	OCH ₃	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	46	238
19.	OH	H	CH ₃	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	33	278d
20.	OH	CH ₃	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ N ₃ O ₂	30	186d
21.	OH	H	NO ₂	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃	36	197d
22.	OH	NO ₂	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃	37	256d
23.	OH	H	Cl	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	38	90d
24.	OH	Cl	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ ClN ₃ O	38	180d
25.	OCH ₃	H	OCH ₃	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	40	239d
26.	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	42	108
27.	OCH ₃	H	CH ₃	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	39	182d
28.	OCH ₃	CH ₃	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₂	39	187d
29.	OCH ₃	H	NO ₂	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	35	203d
30.	OCH ₃	NO ₂	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃	34	232d
31.	OCH ₃	H	Cl	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ ClN ₃ O	35	160d
32.	OCH ₃	Cl	H	CH ₂ N(C ₂ H ₅) ₂	C ₂₆ H ₁₇ ClN ₃ O	33	143d

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

2-(2'-Aryl-6'/7'-substituted-quinoline-4'-yl)-4,5-dihydroimidazoles/benzimidazoles : A mixture of 2-aryl-6/7-substituted-4-quinolinecarboxylic acid (0.01 mol) and ethylenediamine/*o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol) was heated at 160° for 2 h in presence of polyphosphoric acid. The resulting solid products were crystallised (Tables 2 and 3).

2-(2'-Aryl-6'/7'-substituted-quinolin-4'-yl)-N,N-diethylaminomethyl-4,5-dihydroimidazoles/benzimidazoles : A mixture of 2-(2'-aryl-6'/7'-substituted-quinolin-4'-yl)-4,5-dihydroimidazoles/benzimidazole (0.005 mol), formaldehyde (2 ml) and diethylamine (0.005 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 4-5 h. The resulting solid products were crystallised from ethanol (Tables 2 and 3).

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